

Revision of the General Relativity Guided by Enthalpy Conservation

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Abstract

The theory of general relativity boasts incomparable accuracy in both predicting and explaining phenomena to which the exterior Schwarzschild solution is applicable. However, as far as those related to the FLRW metric and the interior Schwarzschild metric are concerned, it has left with us more controversies than legacies. In this paper, I will provide a revision of Einstein's field equation guided by a newly proposed principle of enthalpy conservation, and present a simpler alternative theory of gravity which is compatible with Maxwellian electromagnetism.

In light of the fact that all verifications of the general relativity have been restricted to those related to the exterior Schwarzschild solution where $T_{\mu\nu}$ can be approximated as zero matrix, there is nothing more than our belief of energy conservation on which the validity of the right-hand side of Einstein's equation may stand, thus it actually remains untested to date.

The radius of observable universe is roughly 10^{61} times of the Planck length, whereas the Planck density is roughly 10^{122} times of the current mass density of our universe. Such an improbable coincidence implies that the energy density of our universe may actually be inversely proportional to the square of scale factor, and the total energy in our universe shall be proportional to scale factor.

As a matter of fact, quantum fluctuations alone can hardly explain the existence of a massive universe for billions of years. The principle of energy conservation may only approximately hold true in a time span that is short enough compared with the age of our universe. The positive energy in our universe can only exist as a mirror image balancing with the negative pressure of vacuum space multiplied by volume, such that the enthalpy of our universe conserves at zero ever since its birth from nothing.

$$H = U + PV = 0$$

Guided by this alternative principle, and set $P = -\rho c^2$, then the continuity equation for enthalpy is

$$D_\nu \left(T^{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{4} g^{\mu\nu} T \right) = 0$$

and the field equation ($\Lambda = 0$) shall be revised as

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R = \frac{16\pi G}{c^4} \left(T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} T \right)$$

$$R_{\mu\nu} = \frac{16\pi G}{c^4} \left(T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{3}{4} g_{\mu\nu} T \right)$$

The Friedmann equations ($K = 0$) for an expanding universe are now

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \right)^2 = \frac{4\pi G}{3c^2} (5\rho c^2 - 3P)$$

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3c^2} (\rho c^2 + 9P)$$

$$5\dot{\rho}c^2 - 3\dot{P} = -12\frac{\dot{a}}{a}(\rho c^2 + P)$$

By a mechanism I will address in a separate paper, energy density of our universe shall be inversely proportional to the square of scale factor, such that the cosmological event horizon constantly expands at the velocity of light.

$$\rho \propto a^{-2} \quad \rightarrow \quad \dot{\rho} = -2\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\rho \quad \rightarrow \quad P = -\frac{1}{9}\rho c^2$$

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \right)^2 = H^2 = \frac{64\pi G\rho}{9} \quad \frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = 0$$

By the same mechanism, the total energy in our universe is exactly eight times that of visible matter. The extra seven units are energy of the space with broken symmetry, which is actually the so-called dark matter. In the separate paper, I will discuss the source of discrepancy between my theoretical prediction and the latest data collected by the PLANCK satellite.

Having accepted these assumptions, we may realize with excitement that just 3/8 (or 37.5% which is about 8 times of 4.7%) of the critical density ρ_c back calculated from Einstein's equation can exactly reproduce the observed expanding speed of our universe, without a single Joule of dark energy.

The accelerating expansion of our universe is an illusion due to a time-dependent decrease (inversely proportional to the cubic root of scale factor) of the mass of elementary particles, the mechanism of which will be addressed in the separate paper. By generally blue-shifting the spectra, heavier electron mass can cheat us as if the star light from ancient universe is less red-shifted.

Note that the Friedmann equation for the acceleration of scale factor indicates that the $9P$ in the bracket generally contributes to gravitational acceleration (instead of $3P$ in Einstein's version), it explains the apsidal precession in a much simpler fashion.

Let v be the revolving velocity of Mercury, when v/c is large enough, $T_{\mu\nu}$ of the Sun can no longer be approximated as $diag(\rho c^2, 0, 0, 0)$. Instead,

$$P = \overline{\rho v_x^2} = \overline{\rho v_y^2} = \overline{\rho v_z^2} = \frac{1}{3} \rho v^2$$

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3c^2}(\rho c^2 + 9P) = -\frac{4\pi G}{3} \rho \left(1 + 3 \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)$$

which perfectly gives the effective centripetal force in Schwarzschild solution.

As for why $9P$ contributes to gravity, in the context of enthalpy conservation, evolution of the pressure of matter ($P_m = P$) and the pressure of space (P_s) shall satisfy

$$P_m R^3 = \int_0^R \int_0^r \int_0^\rho dx d\rho dr P_s$$

$$\rightarrow P_m = \frac{1}{6} P_s \quad 9P_m V = \frac{3}{2} P_s V = K$$

K is the kinetic energy confined in the space of volume V , suppose the assembly of matter can be macroscopically approximated as a monoatomic gas. The bracket calculates the sum of rest energy and kinetic energy, both of which act as source of gravity.

Having said all that, any successful revision of general relativity within the original paradigm cannot change its embarrassing incompatibility with quantum mechanics. And here comes the final solution to the stagnation.

In short, the Riemannian geometry in general relativity calculates the sum of three independent gravitational accelerations:

- (1) Dynamics of space, which can be either contraction or expansion, depending on the spatial distribution of mass;
- (2) Universal repulsion between Fermions;
- (3) Contribution from the existence of pressure (attraction when $P > 0$, repulsion when $P < 0$).

The following Maxwellian equations describe a couple of mutual inductive fields \vec{L} and \vec{Y} , which naturally predict the existence of gravitational waves, assuring that gravity does not violate the locality principle.

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{L} = 4\pi G \rho$$

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{Y} = 0$$

$$\nabla \times \vec{L} = -9 \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \vec{Y}}{\partial t}$$

$$\nabla \times \vec{Y} = \frac{1}{9} \left(4\pi G \vec{m} + \frac{\partial \vec{L}}{\partial t} \right)$$

(\vec{m} for 3-momentum density vector.)

Define 4-mass density vector ρ^μ (γ for Lorentz factor), vector potential \vec{G} , scalar potential ϕ , and 4-gravitational potential G^μ .

$$\rho^\mu = \gamma \left(\rho, \frac{\vec{m}}{c} \right) \quad G^\mu = \left(\phi, 9 \frac{\vec{G}}{c} \right)$$

$$\vec{Y} = \nabla \times \vec{G} \quad \vec{L} = -\nabla \phi - 9 \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \vec{G}}{\partial t}$$

Further define field strength tensors $L^{\mu\nu}$ and $\tilde{L}^{\mu\nu}$ in the same manner to Maxwell's tensors $F^{\mu\nu}$ and $\tilde{F}^{\mu\nu}$.

$$L^{\mu\nu} = \partial^\mu G^\nu - \partial^\nu G^\mu \quad \tilde{L}^{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} L_{\rho\sigma}$$

$$L^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & L_1 & L_2 & L_3 \\ -L_1 & 0 & 9Y_3/c & -9Y_2/c \\ -L_2 & -9Y_3/c & 0 & 9Y_1/c \\ -L_3 & 9Y_2/c & -9Y_1/c & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The four equations can be sophisticated as two Lorentz covariant tensor equations.

$$\partial_\nu L^{\mu\nu} = 4\pi G \rho^\mu \quad \partial_\nu \tilde{L}^{\mu\nu} = 0$$

$$R_{00} = \frac{16\pi G}{c^4} \left(\rho c^2 - \frac{3}{4} \rho c^2 \right)$$

To construct the equation of motion, firstly define a 4-vector L^μ from \vec{L} , and a correspondent scalar that calculates the norm of L^μ .

$$\rightarrow R_{00} = \frac{4\pi G}{c^2} \rho - \frac{1}{2} g_{00} R = \frac{16\pi G}{c^2} \rho$$

$$L^\mu = \left(c \frac{d^2 t}{d\tau^2}, \gamma^2 \vec{L} \right) \quad L = \sqrt{L^\mu L_\mu}$$

Then define a mixed tensor σ_ν^μ whose diagonal components take value of either 1 or -1, depending on whether L as a function is increasing or decreasing with regards to the coordinate in question. Lastly, define a correspondent scalar σ by contracting indices.

$$\sigma_\nu^\mu = \frac{\partial_\nu L}{|\partial_\mu L|}$$

$$\sigma = \sigma_\mu^\mu = \begin{cases} 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 = -2 \text{ (Schwarzschild)} \\ 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 = 4 \text{ (Friedmann \cdot Lemaitre)} \end{cases}$$

The equation of motion can be written as

$$\frac{du^\mu}{d\tau} = \frac{L^{\mu\nu} u_\nu}{c} + \sigma L^\mu$$

where u^μ is 4-velocity vector. The contribution from $\vec{u} \times 9\vec{Y}$ and the magnetic component of Lorentz force share a perfect analogy. Rotation in the field of mass (\vec{L}) induces a perpendicular field of pressure (\vec{Y}) whose strength is proportional to the rotating velocity. According to Fleming's left-hand rule, particles running in the field would feel a centripetal force whose strength is now proportional to the square of velocity.

The scalar σ inverts the direction of space dynamics (\vec{L}) when necessary (depending on mass distribution). As we will see shortly, the Newtonian induction of the Friedmann model is neither a temporary expedient nor a childish trick, but rather has wisely pointed out the inherently two-way nature of gravity in a simplest possible manner:

Let $P = 0$, tentatively ignoring the effect of pressure, and focus on the 00 component of the revised field equations.

$$R_{00} - \frac{1}{2} g_{00} R = \frac{16\pi G}{c^4} \left(\rho c^2 + \frac{1}{4} \rho c^2 \right)$$

This calculation coincides with the Newtonian induction shown in below, supposing that space dynamics is twice sensitive as Fermion repulsion in terms of the reactivity to the existence of mass (equivalent to the fact that $\sigma = -2$ in Schwarzschild metric).

Fermion repulsion

$$\frac{d^2 r_m}{dt^2} = G \frac{4\pi r_m^3 \rho}{3} \frac{1}{r_m^2} = \frac{4\pi G \rho}{3} r_m \quad (\rho = \text{const.})$$

$$\rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dr_m}{dt} \right)^2 = \frac{2\pi G \rho}{3} r_m^2 \quad \rightarrow \quad \left(\frac{r_m}{r_m} \right)^2 = \frac{4\pi G \rho}{3}$$

Space dynamics

$$\frac{d^2 r_s}{dt^2} = -2G \frac{4\pi r_s^3 \rho}{3} \frac{1}{r_s^2} = -\frac{8\pi G r_0^3 \rho_0}{3} \frac{1}{r_s^2} \quad (\rho = \rho_0 \frac{r_0^3}{r_s^3})$$

$$\rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dr_s}{dt} \right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G r_0^3 \rho_0}{3} \frac{1}{r_s} \quad \rightarrow \quad \left(\frac{r_s}{r_s} \right)^2 = \frac{16\pi G \rho}{3}$$

It persuasively suggests that the first and second term of Einstein's tensor are actually calculating the contributions from Fermion repulsion and space dynamics respectively. $G_{\mu\nu}$ is endowed with a concrete physical meaning, not just as a result of mathematical induction from Bianchi's identity such that its covariant derivative is structurally zero.

The effect of space shrinkage or expansion can be directly detected as the acceleration of photons perpendicular to their direction of travel. The fact that the bending of light is twice aggressive than that of matter in the periphery of the Sun is nothing but a reflection of the aforementioned difference in their responsiveness to mass.

There is no such thing as universal gravity. The truth behind it is that one unit of centrifugal acceleration (Fermion repulsion) being overwhelmed by two units of centripetal acceleration (space dynamics) in Schwarzschildian mass distribution.